

Pilot Evaluation 1: Developing a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges

Final Version

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Summary

The aim of this pilot project was to develop a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges. Under this pilot were two distinct actions: 1) a Una Europa R&I strategy workshop, and 2) piloting a Horizon Europe Pillar II Call process called matchmaking.

The pilot aligned broadly with the Una.Resin project objectives to create a common, barrier-free R&I eco-system for our researchers and partners, and to strive to make our research increasingly more interdisciplinary and international. Thus, the pilot was linked to all seven transformation modules, but was most closely aligned to the module around developing a common R&I agenda and module focusing on the exploration of joint university structures.

Una Europa R&I strategy workshop

The aim of this pilot activity was to develop an online format for strategic future discussions to identify emerging research areas in interdisciplinary collaborative settings. The research community holds great insight regarding future developments but, due to the slow self-correcting nature of research, researchers are sometimes hesitant to co-create and express their insights prior to pre-reviewed processes. This pilot aimed to find a way to encourage academics to discuss their insights and find new collaborations beyond their research fields. The format the project opted to pilot was an online workshop preceded by a pre-assignment.

The workshop consisted of keynotes and facilitated group discussions. To lead the participants in the grand challenges approach and the EU's "Approach to International R&I Collaboration in a Changing World", the workshop included two keynote speeches: Aleksi Neuvonen, Demos Helsinki think tank, and Nienke Buisman, Head of Unit, Directorate-General for R&I, Global Approach & International Partnerships, International Cooperation. The workshop was co-designed and co-facilitated by the think tank Demos Helsinki.

The feedback from attendees was generally positive and enthusiastic. Many participants found that they lacked the skills and traditions required for this kind of multi-/interdisciplinary workshop approach and valued an introduction to this working method. There is future potential to use this workshop format when developing the Una Europa Focus Areas into interdisciplinary hubs and as part of the community engagement in the general Una Europa strategic work. However, further use of co-creative workshops will necessitate dedicated ownership within the Alliance for both their organisation and facilitation.

Piloting a process Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking

The aim of this pilot activity was to develop a process for interdisciplinary matchmaking for Horizon Europe Pillar II calls. According to the Una.Resin WP1 benchmarking phase, there is a major interest and unused potential in our Alliance regarding European funding, and

particularly, Horizon Europe Pillar II funding. Whilst most partner universities have existing support service structures, there is potential to build systematic and sustainable support for the calls at an Una Europa level and to share best practice. The pilot project identified the enabling and hindering structures, processes, and cultures at the partner universities and at the Alliance level, whilst sharing best practice and tools to create an ideal process.

The pilot action was designed and facilitated in close collaboration with the Una Europa Research Coordination Cluster, the One Health self-steering committee, and the Una Europa vzw external funding manager. Jean-Charles Cavitte, an EC Research Policy Officer, provided a keynote at the first of the two matchmaking workshops, which familiarised participants with EC policy and EU-funded research linked to One Health.

The feedback from participants was positive and illustrated how, with refinement, the matchmaking format offered a highly successful approach for responding to interdisciplinary funding Horizon Europe Pillar II calls. The tight schedule and the process for identifying proposal coordinators was the most problematic element of the pilot.

In the Horizon Pillar II matchmaking process, the Alliance should support the following: 1) identifying topics and coordinators (starting point); 2) collecting Expressions of Interest (Eols); 3) matchmaking workshops; and 4) general information sessions about the funding instrument. On the other hand, the proposal writing support – including grant writer resources and potential travel funds – should be provided by the coordinating university. We also learned that there is a need for an online platform allowing for the interactive collection of Eols.

The most important **outcome** of the pilot was the development of the co-creation workshop and matchmaking formats and processes themselves, which are ready for future use. The pilot allowed us to develop and test the processes step-by-step and to identify the tools, skills, and human resources needed to collaboratively pursue an interdisciplinary pathway.

In terms of **lessons learnt**, it should be noted that organising these kinds of workshops or matchmaking events is time-intensive and requires an understanding of local contexts and networks. The process and the tools are not enough, with skilled facilitators and systematic communication also being key for success. The universities should consider the designing and facilitation of collaborative workshops, both online and on-site, as a specialist skill of research professionals, and dedicated training for the development of this skill would be highly beneficial. To accelerate interdisciplinary research collaboration, Una Europa must pay more attention to matching Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) fields and foster collaboration across Focus Areas.

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The aim of the pilot was to develop and test methods to accelerate cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration and networking in addressing the Una Europa priority global challenges. This comprised of two separate actions: 1) a Una Europa R&I strategy workshop and 2) piloting a process Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking. Via these two actions, the pilot sought to understand the barriers and enablers in the following areas:

- Building the Una Europa Network for collaborative research:
 - The areas targeted in particular: international research collaboration, research

infrastructures, ecosystems with non-academic actors and research lifecycle (e.g., sharing, management, support, training personnel, opening collaboration to non-academic organisational partners and citizens).

- Working cultures:
 - Inter-, Trans-, Crossdisciplinarity and challenge-based approach in research collaboration.
 - Co-creation of a workshop-type in the research context.
 - Foresight and futures literacy, and understanding the grand challenges in the context of excellence and impact (the key goals of the Una Europa partner universities).
- Institutional processes:
 - General institutional enablers and barriers for international research collaboration.
 - Support for research funding: alignment of the structures and priorities of the partner universities.
- Incentives and practices for researchers to build a successful Horizon Europa Pillar II proposal.

The pilot also aimed to satisfy the following aims when planning and appointing the participants and speakers for both the workshop and matchmaking event:

- Equality both from the gender and the career stage perspective;
- Emphasising the safe space for new ideas; and
- The European Commission (EC) context both in terms of the grand challenges and research funding instruments.

The approach was comprehensive and, thus, linked to all seven transformation modules. However, the most directly addressed transformation modules were: 1) develop a common R&I agenda, and 7) explore joint university structures. In term of institution change, the objective of the pilot are closely linked to the following modules: 1) develop activities to anticipate the potential social, environmental, and economic impacts of research (e.g., risk assessment, threat assessment, foresight, impact assessment, gender analysis; 2) help develop R&I standards that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness, sustainability of R&I processes and products; 3) develop material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), public engagement, ethics, gender); and 4) enlarge the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, engaging civil society actors and citizens.

The pilot primarily aimed to target the Una.Resin project itself by informing the R&I strategy development. In addition to creating an online working format, the workshop aimed to identify research themes the Una Europa community deems as important in the future to respond to the grand challenges and identify enablers and barriers to international research collaboration. In addition, the pilot also intended to target research performing organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaged in Research & Development (R&D), citizens and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), and public authorities. The beneficiaries of the pilot are Una Europa organisations and participating researchers.

Simultaneously to the pilot, the University of Helsinki was developing a roadmap to implement

its strategic aim of interdisciplinary research. The process was conducted in an innovative way using the methods of co-creation. It provided many useful pedagogical learnings for our pilot about how to engage workshop participants and the mindset of co-learning.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

Una Europa R&I strategy workshop

The pilot “developing a format for supporting systematic collaboration on the Una Europa priority global challenges” was originally scheduled to take place in the second half of the Una.Resin project. The COVID-19 pandemic forced the pilot to move online and, consequently, a workshop that could be hosted and delivered online was designed. The pandemic complicated not only the implementation of the pilot, but also the development of the Una Europa R&I strategy, which is the flagship development of the Una.Resin project. The workshop, however, provided a space to collect insights to feed into the Una Europa R&I strategy development. The workshop aimed to identify the true needs of researchers and the barriers that they perceive as potentially hindering Una Europa R&I collaboration, as well as the challenges of building a larger ecosystem. Based on these aims, a three-hour online workshop was designed that was preceded by a pre-assignment.

During the planning phase, continuous discussions were held with Una Europa vzw and with the team preparing the Una Europa 2030 strategy. The process and the relevant working questions were designed with other Una.Resin Work Packages (WPs) and the research coordination cluster members. The Una.Resin project managers at each partner university provided necessary support by identifying and inviting participants for the workshop. The Una.Resin WP2 colleagues helped articulate relevant questions around research infrastructures and their input ensure that the workshop outcomes also satisfied their work towards the Una Europa Research Infrastructure and Resources (RIR) strategy. The Demos Helsinki Think Tank, who have vast experience of organising co-creative futures workshops, were recruited to support with designing and facilitating the R&I strategy workshop. The discussion groups were facilitated by colleagues from the Una Europa Research Coordination Cluster and other Una.Resin WP members.

The pre-assignment sought to tune participants to potential future visions and emerging research themes, whilst also supporting the preparation of workshop discussion questions. As most of the participants were not familiar with Una Europa, a series of materials were provided including information on the excellence of the Una Europa universities, on the Alliance’s current priority areas, on the grand challenges¹ and key strategic orientations, on the Horizon Europe clusters, and on the UN Sustainable Development goals (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>). As a technical solution, the interactive on-line platform Flinga (<https://flinga.fi/>) was utilised.

The online workshop consisted of two parts. First, there were keynotes addressing Una Europa, grand challenges, and the EU’s approach to international R&I collaboration in a changing world. The second part of the workshop consisted of group discussions, where online canvases were used to structure the discussions. Each group had their own facilitator.

The following challenges were faced, and overcome, in designing and implementing the Una Europa R&I strategy workshop:

¹ The grand challenges materials were produced by Sitra (<https://www.sitra.fi/en/>) and Demos Helsinki.

- This type of online co-working, as well as the interdisciplinary futures approach, was largely new to both the research professionals involved in planning and facilitating and the academic participants. At the time of the workshop, Una Europa was relatively new and unknown resulting in some resistance from the project side to this novel approach. The pre-assignment aimed to address this challenge. However, the pre-assignment turned out to be too complicated, with too many materials provided. There was also confusion from the researchers about the purpose of the workshop, which was perceived as not directly related to their current research. However, during and after the workshop and once participants were familiar with the new way of working, there was excitement in the air and many participants expressed interest in a follow-up workshop.
- There were cultural differences among participants in terms of both familiarity with online working and with co-creation working. The involvement of researchers from different career stages, research fields, and cultural backgrounds was emphasised, but it was challenge to get a sound representation as participant numbers had to be limited to six per partner university. In future, special emphasis should be put on expanding the target group to citizens and non-academics with diverse backgrounds. However, five participants plus the facilitator proved to be a suitable group size for this type of workshop.
- Unfortunately, not all registered participants showed up and there were participants coming and going throughout the workshop. This underlined the essential role of facilitators who could reorganise the groups during the workshop. The disappearance of the participants during the workshop must be anticipated and there must be a readiness to reform the groups if needed.
- Due to the tight planning schedule, there was limited time to brief facilitators prior to the workshop and the facilitator role was new to many of those supporting the delivery of the workshop. In future, the universities should consider hosting collaborative workshops both online and in-person. Designing and facilitating co-creation workshops could be promoted as a special skill for research professionals, with the provision of specific training to support the development of this skill.
- Project budget was very limited, and Demos Helsinki provided support at a low cost due to their personal interest. Their support was integral to creating a successful workshop format for future use.

Piloting a process Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking

The initiative to pilot matchmaking under the Horizon Europe Pillar II call came from the Una Europa One self-steering committee and from the Una Europa external funding officer. Matchmaking aligned with the pilots aim to further develop methods to accelerate cross-disciplinary and cross-sectoral collaboration in addressing the priority challenges, as well as to the format and the lessons learnt from the Una Europa R&I strategy workshop.

The whole process, from first planning meetings to the evaluation phase, lasted from February 2022 until September 2023. The pilot included the following steps:

1. Collection of Eols via the online Lyyti platform (<https://www.lyyti.com/en/>).
2. Identification and briefing of potential coordinators.
3. An online workshop that included a general session highlighting European goals and the particularities of the Horizon Europe Pillar II call, as well as a facilitated group discussion aimed at drafting the core idea of the proposal and appointing the core group for the

proposal preparation. This online workshop was based on the template created in the R&I strategy workshop (Zoom as a meeting platform and Google Slides for the online canvases).

4. A hybrid (online and in-person) workshop for the groups of researchers who engaged with proposal preparation (Teams). In this workshop the participants had a chance to:
 - 1) learn about the particularities of the call and proposal writing in the plenary sessions,
 - 2) get support for the proposal drafting, and
 - 3) participate in the Una Europa One Health networking event. The workshop was organised in connection to the Una Europa General Assembly.
5. A proposal preparation phase.
6. An online evaluation questionnaire after the process (Lyyti platform).

The pilot action was designed in close collaboration with several Una Europa bodies via online and in-person meetings and workshops. The Una Europa Research Coordination Cluster (RCC) had a pivotal role in understanding the internal processes and shared best practices from their home institutions, e.g., the ideal questions for the EoI template. The RCC identified the contact points for academics, as well as a pathway for approaching research funding professionals. The group also had an essential role in advising on the particularities of European funding and the local research funding service structures and processes. The One Health self-steering committee acted as the academic owner of the process. The RCC and One Health self-steering committee provided an important understanding of the needs of the academics participating involved and identified the themes from the Horizon Europe Pillar II Call that the matchmaking event centred around. The Una Europa vzw external funding manager supported with the identification of the roles and provided up-to-date information about the Pillar II call preparation status. Una Europa vzw also supported with the identification and invitation of the keynote speaker, Jean-Charles Cavitte (EC Research Policy Officer), of the online workshop, who presented insights on policy and EU-funded research in the area of One Health. In addition, each academic group preparing a proposal was supported by an experienced research funding professional appointed by two Una Europa universities, the University of Helsinki and the KU Leuven.

The Una Europa external funding officer conducted the preselection activity, listing 37 Horizon Europe Pillar II call topics that were presented to the One Health self-steering committee. In the end, four topics were chosen. The EoI invitation was sent to 74 academics representing the Una Europa Focus Areas, who were asked to share the invitations with their colleagues. The EoI invitation was also shared by the RCC using the internal channels at the partner institutions. In the EoI phase, 79 answers were received from five Una Europa universities. Due to minimal interest in one of the topics, three were chosen for the online workshop. There were 35 academics participating in the workshop from the same five universities, with research professionals facilitating and observing the workshop. Finally, there were 30 participants in the hybrid proposal preparation meeting. The evaluation questionnaire was sent to everyone who received the original EoI invitation, and 12 answers were received from the same five universities that were involved from the beginning of the process.

The following challenges were faced in piloting the Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking process, which also offer a number of recommendations:

- The aim was to have research participants from various fields across STEM and the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) subjects. To meet this aim, the short call

descriptions indicated SSH input was essential for a successful proposal, even where the call was One Health focused. We advertised the matchmaking to all Focus Areas and relevant researchers at all universities. Still, mainly natural scientists were interested. As the Una Europa Focus Areas are further developed into research hubs, cross-focus matchmaking and bi-annual strategic workshops aimed at each focus area, self-steering committees and different career-stage researchers should give serious consideration to build long-term collaboration and develop the in-depth understanding required for new knowledge and the development of successful proposals. Increasingly general awareness of Una Europa and the common communication channels should further support this aim.

- The message we got from our research community was, that besides the matchmaking, they also wished for grant writing support from Una Europa. The pilot illustrated how the level of support at the proposal preparation stage differs across the partner universities. In all cases, the most extensive support (including an appointed grant writer) is provided only to the proposals coordinated by the university and securing this support is generally not possible in Una Europa. One of the nine involved partner universities has an internal selection process for proposals coordinated by them, and so, it is important to ensure that the Una Europa process now, or in the future, do not conflict with this process. In this pilot, we navigated the above-mentioned conditions and needs by 1) providing general presentations about the Horizon Europe Pilar II particularities, and 2) inviting grant coaches from the coordinating universities to the onsite workshop at KU Leuven.
- We planned to use an interactive platform for collecting Eols. The idea was that in an ideal situation the researchers could have initiated the discussion about the research topics already online. There were some platforms, like B2B, that would have been suitable and reasonably priced. However, they were still too expensive for our very limited project budget. Instead, we used an online questionnaire platform, which allowed us to turn the answers into an excel format and, in the end, to a sharable catalogue. The University of Helsinki (UH) appointed additional human resources to do this. Manually creating shareable catalogues is time intensive and Una Europa should consider investing in an online platform, making this phase both easy and interactive in the future.
- The schedule of the pilot was tight and we needed to proceed at full speed, learning as we went. The tight timeframe resulted in a degree of confusion when running the workshops. The time gap between the online and the in-person workshops was short and left little time for travel arrangements, and the participating academics asked us to organise the meeting in a hybrid mode to allow them all to participate. However, a hybrid meeting may not have been the most suitable mode for the workshop with one participant stating: “Very few attendees were present in Leuven. Interaction through mixed channels (in-person plus online) is difficult and time-consuming.” Another participant provided the following feedback: “The hybrid mode (online and onsite) especially, was not suitable for in-depth planning and discussion”. There was also major confusion that the workshop was an Una Europa signature event and there was support with travel costs, which was not the case. The difficulties experienced in the implementation of the workshop did, however, produced a valuable understanding of the expectations.
- Appointing coordinators was challenging. We received a lot of Eols to participate in the call, but few experienced researchers were interested in coordinating calls. In the evaluation phase, we received the most negative feedback. This was mostly due to the

tight schedule. We had very little time to identify and brief the potential coordinators before the online workshop. Moreover, throughout the pilot, as well as during the two workshops, we had problems with engagement and participants jumping between the call topic groups. This made it hard for the coordinators to identify their “own” group. In the future, it would make sense to have separate workshops for each topic.

- We received only 12 answers to the pilot evaluation form, despite indicating to participants that feedback would be used for development purposes. It would make sense to ask for feedback after the end of each stage, when it is still fresh in the memory of the participants.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

With this pilot we aimed to understand the institutional barriers and identify enablers to create conditions for barrier-free collaboration. The pilot provided essential understanding for the Una Europa R&I strategy preparation and resulted in two submitted Horizon Europe Pillar II consortium proposals. One of the two made it to the reserve list. In addition, one proposal was prepared, but not submitted in this round. These are very concrete outcomes. The most important outcome of the pilot was the development of the workshop and matchmaking processes that are now ready for the future use. The pilot allowed us to develop and test the process step by step and to identify the tools, skills, and human resources needed to carry out such creative collaborative interdisciplinary processes. The outcomes have been presented in more detail in the Una.Resin WP1 deliverable D1.1.

The Una Europa Focus Areas serve as excellent communities for the creation of interdisciplinary understanding and cross-discipline matchmaking. Matchmaking seems to be particularly effective within the Alliance context because there are additional drivers for cooperation (e.g., institutional support and strategic alignment). We have already shared the lessons learnt with the Unite!, an alliance of research intensive and technical universities, and have identified collaboration opportunities to respond to interdisciplinary consortium calls in the area of sustainability.

The EC has asked Una Europa for more bottom-up collaborative research opportunities that are both open in scope and allow for interdisciplinary research perspectives. Una Europa is committed in its strategies (i.e., the Una Europa 2030 strategy and the Una Europa R&I strategy) to support bold interdisciplinary research and empower early-career researchers. The pilot provides essential tools and a new kind of mindset to explore inter-, trans- and multidisciplinary cooperation around the R&I activities in Una Europa and beyond. The R&I strategy workshop provided an experimental approach to increase understanding and support researchers in identifying weakness in emerging research areas that are pivotal for responding to the grand challenges of our time. The Horizon Pillar II process takes this to a more practical level and provides concrete tools for matchmaking and proposal ideation.

The feedback from the attendees of the R&I strategy, co-creation workshop was positive. However, some participants found that they lacked skills and traditions for this kind of multi-/interdisciplinary approach and would have benefitted from a more comprehensive introduction to this working method. We found that the research themes raised in this workshop were often crosscutting, reflecting scientific understandings that the grand challenges are interlinked and cannot be treated as separate phenomena. Terminologies and

approaches such as “grand challenges” are hence not always the most fruitful way to engage researchers with this kind of workshop, as researchers tend to formulate their interests within the terminology and culture of their discipline. Una Europa is in an excellent position to share understanding between the research community and European decision makers.

The participants of the Horizon Europe Pillar II Call matchmaking represented five of the (at the time) nine Una Europa universities. Not getting Eols from four of the universities reflects partly the One Health focus, but also the difference in the funding policies in the different partner countries. In some of the universities there is a strong national funding base, and the Horizon Europe calls are considered administratively heavy and thus not desired. In addition, at the time of our pilot, the UK member association to the Horizon Europe was still not secure and it was unclear if the UK participating university would be eligible for Horizon Europe funding. However, the feedback illustrated that the pilot was found most successful in “establishing new contacts” and “learning about consortium-based proposal preparation”; this is a remarkable outcome.

In particular, the workshop and matchmaking provided an opportunity for the early career researchers to widen their networks. Una Europa stands for diversity, academic freedom, and well-being, and the pilot indicates how institutional barriers and hierarchies could be overcome should alliances have the opportunity to propose call initiatives. The process also provides early career researchers with an opportunity to learn about the proposal process and the Horizon projects, preparing them to become coordinators themselves in the future.

Researchers’ feedback to the Una Europa pilot on Horizon Europe matchmaking

Following the matchmaking event, feedback was collected from researchers who participated in the event. The feedback consultation period ran from the 20/06/2023 to the 15/09/2023 and took the form of a questionnaire, which also provided an opportunity to collect more general feedback (see Figure 1). The feedback gained tended to be positive (see Figure 2 and Figure 3) and has proven instrumental in understanding and collating lessons learnt and guiding the resulting recommendations.

Participant A: “In general, the whole strategy was well devised. With the lessons learned we for sure can refine and mature this approach to have a winning recipe for funding.”

Participant B: “The Una Europa pilot for matchmaking was useful to discover opportunities and get to know complementary research teams in participating universities. Sadly enough, the mechanics of the proposal preparation were not targeted enough towards a winner application (as it happens in other proposals outside the Una Europa umbrella...).”

Participant C: “The idea to support proposal building for EU calls is great but I think the process needs to start earlier to allow the participants to really connect and know each other. More work with the potential coordinators in the beginning to consider the proposal text and scope.”

Figure 1: General feedback from researchers who participated in the matchmaking event

Figure 2: Participants' answers to the question "I found the pilot helpful for..." (multiple answers allowed)

Figure 3: Participants' answers to the question "How satisfied were you with the different pilot phases?"

Question	Yes	No	Do not know
Was the structure of the workshop appropriate?	10	0	0
Did you find the templates and facilitation appropriate?	9	0	1
Did you find the presentations useful?	10	0	0
Did you find the technical platforms appropriate (Zoom & Google sheets)?	9	0	1

Table 1: Participants' answers in relation to the online workshop

Sustainability of the pilot project

In the coming years, the Una Europa Focus Areas are developing into interdisciplinary hubs for research and education. The hubs widen the ecosystem beyond academia to encompass local actors in the partner countries. Co-creation of the strategic understanding and cross-focus area matchmaking will have a pivotal role in this development. The Una Europa R&I strategy format supports this work perfectly. The workshop format could also be useful as part of the continuous, collaborative strategic work that is essential for this kind of Alliance. However, there is not yet a recognised owner who could facilitate such a workshop in the Alliance.

We are very confident that the Horizon Pillar II matchmaking process will be scaled up to a continuous Una Europa process. This process was included as a recommended action in the Una Europa R&I Funding Pathway (Una Europa R&I strategy Annex 1, WP1 Delivery 1.2.). As part of the R&I strategy implementation Roadmap (Una Europa R&I strategy Annex 2, WP1 Deliverable 1.2), the Una Europa partner institutions are currently discussing how the activities to implement the Una Europa R&I strategy should be prioritised. This process was prioritised with the highest score by the Una Europa vice rectors of research in their meeting on the 11th October 2023.

The Una Europa RCC, the expert group of research funding advisors, has now been appointed as a permanent Una Europa body. This is largely because of the learnings we gained in this pilot and the RCC has already taken ownership of the matchmaking process. There is also natural continuity as UH was the responsible organisation for this pilot and the RCC is chaired by UH. Thus, all lessons learnt and the formats created will be handed over to the future users.

The Una Europa Focus Areas are excellent incubators of interdisciplinary ideas and understanding. The Pillar II topics are still to be defined, and there may be rather little time to prepare the proposals after the call is announced. This leads to suboptimal processes and makes it difficult to ensure inclusivity of matchmaking. Bottom-up interdisciplinary funding would solve this.

Non-academic collaborations are crucial to successful consortium proposals and one of the ambitious aims of the Una.Resin project was to find ways to collaborate with non-academic partners throughout the Una Europa R&I ecosystem. However, developing such an ecosystem takes time. At the stage of planning the pilot, we did not have a ready ecosystem to reach out to. As our primary aim was to learn about the structures and processes at the partner universities and pilot the process on the Una Europa level, we decided to restrict the participation to the Una Europa level but invite some external key-note speakers. As a next step, the process should be further developed at an institutional level to build ways to systematically identify infrastructures and non-academic collaborations relevant for the proposals. Support for responding to Pillar II and other major European research funding opportunities should be pro-active and the highest priority for the new vzw External Funding Officer. Alliance-level industry collaboration, like common fairs, is not a priority at this stage but should be a longer-term goal. Connection with industry and societal actors should draw from the activities of academic hubs, such as doctoral education activities and funding calls.

Una Europa institutions are global actors, and as an Alliance, we have an even broader reach. Understanding this reach as a responsibility and opportunity to address global challenges from diverse perspectives, Una Europa aims to establish multi-lateral global partnerships and engage global talent. The collaboration with the Una Europa strategic partner higher education institutions in Africa is progressively taking shape, and Una Europa should involve African partner institutions more systematically in matchmaking. In addition, Una Europa should support partners in solving mobility issues, like visas, of the African collaborators in participating the events organised in Europe.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing this pilot:

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- Participants of both the R&I strategy workshop and the Horizon Europe Pillar II matchmaking process were eager and pleased to work together, confirming there is a vast, largely untapped potential for this type of Una Europa-led research collaboration.
- In the Horizon Europe Pillar II matchmaking process, the Una Europa External funding offices and the RCC should support the following: 1) identification of the topics and coordinators; 2) collection of the Eols; 3) matchmaking workshops; and 4) general information sessions about the funding instrument. The proposal writing support, including grant writer resources and potential travel funds, should be provided by the coordinating university. This must be communicated clearly.
- Due to the Una.Resin project, the One Health self-steering committee meeting and the Una Europa general assembly schedules, the Pillar II matchmaking process started too late leaving little time between the two workshops and for the identification of the coordinators. In the future, time between the different phases of the process needs to be built into the schedule. However, the consolidation of research cooperation in Focus Areas and increased awareness of the Alliance among the academic community should also contribute to the readiness to prepare joint applications.
- Organising this kind of workshop is time intensive and requires an understanding of local contexts and networks. The process and the tools are not enough, with skilled facilitators and systematic communication also being key for success. It is important to make sure that the universities appoint working time of the RCC members and other relevant professionals for the facilitation of such workshops and processes.
- The co-creation concept, futures approach, and online workshops are new to many academics. As an example, the workshop started with a discussion instead of passive listening to encourage the participants to become active owners of the workshop rather than passive followers. This format can be initially confusing to participants, who tend to be more familiar with others setting the agenda and the tone of workshops. Despite initial discomfort, participants were willing to collaborate from the outset and build ideas together. Una Europa should pay attention to innovative pedagogies in the future, even if it is not always the most familiar or common way to run a workshop.

Recommendations for the future

The pilot offers a number of recommendations giving direction to future activity:

- There is a need for an online platform allowing interactive collection of Eols. Una Europa could use an existing platform in the short term and, in the longer term, European platforms could be developed. In the short term, Una Europa should also share links to the research portals of each partner university. In the longer term, Una Europa could develop a way to harvest existing data from the research portals to support matchmaking.
- The universities should consider designing and facilitating collaborative workshops, both online and in-person. This could constitute a special skill for the research professionals and would require specific training.
- Una Europa must pay more attention to matching the SSH and STEM fields and foster interdisciplinary collaboration. Communication with participants illustrated how the community believe more can be done in this arena and Una Europa have a role to play in fostering a collaborative mindset across the Alliance.
- Una Europa should consider ways to fund mobility to advance consortium building. The current situation, where some universities and some fields have funding and others do

- not, creates inequality and is a barrier to excellence.
- Una Europa should put special emphasis on developing ways to involve non-academic collaborators to the consortium at an institutional level.